

Explore

Notes

Output Created		01-SEP-2024 21:54:27
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\jkroa\Documents\Course Work\AntsAnalysis\SimData.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet2
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	6023
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values for dependent variables are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on cases with no missing values for any dependent variable or factor used.
Syntax		EXAMINE VARIABLES=SmlArenaPerm MedArenaPerm LrgArenaPerm BY Type /PLOT BOXPLOT STEMLEAF NPLOT /COMPARE GROUPS /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES /CINTERVAL 95 /MISSING LISTWISE /NOTOTAL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:02.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:02.08

Type

Case Processing Summary

	Type	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
SmlArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
	Random	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
MedArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
	Random	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
LrgArenaPerm	Beacon	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%
	Random	3003	100.0%	0	0.0%	3003	100.0%

Descriptives

		Type	Statistic	Std. Error	
SmlArenaPerm	Beacon	Mean	308.9703	.97202	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	307.0644	
			Upper Bound	310.8762	
		5% Trimmed Mean	308.0549		
		Median	304.8967		
		Variance	2837.308		
		Std. Deviation	53.26639		
		Minimum	187.93		
		Maximum	471.00		
		Range	283.07		
		Interquartile Range	78.71		
		Skewness	.261	.045	
		Kurtosis	-.547	.089	
		Random	Mean	306.7501	.97202
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	304.8442	
			Upper Bound	308.6560	
	5% Trimmed Mean		307.6655		
	Median		310.8237		
	Variance		2837.308		
	Std. Deviation		53.26639		
	Minimum		144.72		
	Maximum		427.80		
	Range		283.07		
Interquartile Range	78.71				
Skewness	-.261	.045			
Kurtosis	-.547	.089			
MedArenaPerm	Beacon	Mean	485.6369	1.08611	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	483.5073	
			Upper Bound	487.7665	
		5% Trimmed Mean	484.5258		
		Median	483.3528		
		Variance	3542.438		
		Std. Deviation	59.51838		
		Minimum	351.73		
		Maximum	675.08		
		Range	323.35		
		Interquartile Range	85.75		
		Skewness	.235	.045	
		Kurtosis	-.437	.089	
		Random	Mean	440.8990	1.08611
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	438.7694	
			Upper Bound	443.0286	
	5% Trimmed Mean		442.0101		

Descriptives

Type		Statistic	Std. Error	
		Median	443.1831	
		Variance	3542.438	
		Std. Deviation	59.51838	
		Minimum	251.46	
		Maximum	574.81	
		Range	323.35	
		Interquartile Range	85.75	
		Skewness	-.235	
		Kurtosis	-.437	
LrgArenaPerm	Beacon	Mean	585.4842	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean		
		Lower Bound	584.0004	
		Upper Bound	586.9680	
		5% Trimmed Mean	585.5048	
		Median	585.6852	
		Variance	1719.733	
		Std. Deviation	41.46967	
		Minimum	454.77	
		Maximum	709.76	
		Range	255.00	
		Interquartile Range	57.55	
		Skewness	-.008	
	Kurtosis	-.266		
		Random	Mean	512.8244
			95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
			Lower Bound	511.3406
			Upper Bound	514.3082
			5% Trimmed Mean	512.8037
			Median	512.6234
		Variance	1719.733	
		Std. Deviation	41.46967	
		Minimum	388.55	
		Maximum	643.54	
		Range	255.00	
		Interquartile Range	57.55	
		Skewness	.008	
		Kurtosis	-.266	

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of MedArenaPerm
for Type= Beacon

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of MedArenaPerm
for Type= Random

LrgArenaPerm

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

LrgArenaPerm Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Type= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
3.00	Extremes (<=468)
6.00	47 . 1&
20.00	48 . 047&
25.00	49 . 1679&
47.00	50 . 01123477&
81.00	51 . 012233345566677788999
102.00	52 . 0012223344555677888999999
148.00	53 . 01112222333444455556666777888999999
180.00	54 . 0001111122233334444555566667778889999999
212.00	55 . 00000111122222233344444555566667778888889999999
250.00	56 . 000001111112222223333444445555566666777777788889999999
272.00	57 . 000000111111122222233334444445555566666677777788889999999
282.00	58 . 00000011111112222223333444444555556666667777778888889999999
269.00	59 . 00000011111112222223333444444555556666677777788888899999
260.00	60 . 0000000111122222233333344444455556666677777788888999999
217.00	61 . 000011112222223334444555566667777888899999
185.00	62 . 0000011112222333344444555666677788899999
153.00	63 . 000001122233344445556667778889999
106.00	64 . 00011222334455667788999
78.00	65 . 00112234455667789
51.00	66 . 011223456789
27.00	67 . 12347&
18.00	68 . 27&&
8.00	69 . &&
3.00	Extremes (>=704)

Stem width: 10.00
 Each leaf: 4 case(s)

& denotes fractional leaves.

LrgArenaPerm Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
 Type= Random

Frequency	Stem &	Leaf
3.00 Extremes (<=394)		
1.00	39 .	&
9.00	40 .	9&&
20.00	41 .	03456789&
31.00	42 .	01234567889
52.00	43 .	01123345566677899
87.00	44 .	001112233344455566677888999
111.00	45 .	001112223333444455556667777788889999
160.00	46 .	0000111122222333333444445555566667777788888999999
193.00	47 .	000001111122222233333344444455555666666667777788888889999999
220.00	48 .	0000000111111122222233333344444444455555556666667777778888888999999
9		
262.00	49 .	0000000001111111111222233333333344444444455555555566666677777777888
888889999999999		
270.00	50 .	0000000000111111122222222333333334444444445555555556666666667777777
78888888889999999		
279.00	51 .	0000000001111111111122222222333333444444444555555556666666667777
7777788888888999999		
271.00	52 .	00000000001111111112222222333333334444444445555566666666677777777
88888888899999999		
252.00	53 .	00000000111111122222222233333333444444455555566666666777777788888
88889999999		
209.00	54 .	000000111111122222233333334444444555556666667777778888888999999
174.00	55 .	00000001111122222333333344444445555666666777888888999999
146.00	56 .	000001111122222333334444445555566667788888899999
88.00	57 .	000112233344445556677888889
71.00	58 .	0001111222344555566799&
47.00	59 .	00112344455667888
19.00	60 .	11257&
19.00	61 .	013358&
6.00	62 .	6&
3.00 Extremes (>=630)		

Stem width: 10.00
 Each leaf: 3 case(s)

& denotes fractional leaves.

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

